

Asymmetrical Forest: My Reflection on the Visual Metaphors of Open Science

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1. Introduction: A Workshop in “Doing Open Science”

In September 2025, I participated in a workshop at the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) in Rome, as part of my fellowship at the Institute for the European Intellectual Lexicon and History of Ideas (ILIESI) supported by OPERAS TNA. The event was not a conventional academic seminar. Its objective, guided by the thoughtful work of the organizers, was to enact the very principles of Open Science in the process of co-authoring a collective volume on the subject. The gathering was designed as a living experiment in collaborative knowledge creation, seeking to embody the epistemic commitments of openness, plurality, and participation.

The central focus of the discussions was the work of Francesca Di Donato (CNR–ILC), who presented a chapter from her ongoing research on the visual metaphors that have shaped the development of the Open Science movement (Di Donato 2025). Her analysis foregrounded the ways in which images—whether umbrella, mushroom, wheel, tree, graph, or forest—function not as neutral illustrations but as constitutive frameworks that structure meaning, orient practices, and reveal cultural assumptions.

This reflection is both personal and scholarly. It situates itself within the workshop’s intellectual milieu while extending Di Donato’s argument toward a critical re-reading of the **forest** metaphor, with attention to its inherent asymmetries. My colleague Ramazan Turgut and I were able to join this group of scholars thanks to the generous support of Cristina Marras (CNR–ILIESI), whose intellectual leadership and dedication to the project were instrumental. The workshop was mainly conducted in Italian, which added a rewarding dimension of cross-cultural engagement to our experience.

The aim of this article is thus twofold: first, to trace the conceptual trajectory of Open Science metaphors as presented by Di Donato; second, to contribute a critical and pragmatic extension that interrogates both the strengths and the limitations of the forest image. In doing so, the metaphor of the ocean may provide an alternative horizon, more fluid and nuanced, for re-imagining the epistemic space of Open Science.

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2. The Evolution of Metaphors in Open Science

2.1 Context and Attribution

Visual metaphors are not peripheral embellishments in the discourse of Open Science; they are central to its conceptual articulation. They define boundaries, assign value, and embody cultural assumptions about what openness in science should mean. As Cristina Marras has emphasized in her work on metaphors and pragmatic modelling, such images are constitutive operators rather than descriptive ornaments: they organize thought and guide practice. The following overview traces the evolution of key metaphors identified by Francesca Di Donato in her analysis, which moves from man-made artifacts to natural and ecological systems.

2.2 The Umbrella and the Mushroom

The earliest prominent metaphor is the **umbrella**, introduced by (Fecher and Friesike 2014) to capture the multiple “schools of thought” that constitute Open Science. The umbrella serves as a human-made tool: a unifying device that brings together different practices—such as open access, open data, and citizen science—under a single conceptual framework. Yet, as Di Donato noted, different communities deploy this image with divergent emphases, as seen in initiatives such as Public & Science (Sweden), the EOSC-hub project, and FIOCRUZ (Brazil).

A decisive shift occurred with Eva Méndez’s “mushroom” metaphor. The mushroom introduces a biological model in place of an artifact, emphasizing not only visible practices but also the hidden infrastructures that sustain them. Its anatomy encodes this conceptual structure: the gills represent citizen science, the stem denotes standards and governance, and the subterranean mycelium symbolizes integrity, infrastructure, and evaluation systems. This image foregrounds the unseen supports upon which Open Science depends.

2.3 The Wheel and the Tree

The next stage in metaphorical development is the **wheel**, proposed by Kramer and Bosman (2017). The wheel represents Open Science as a continuous, circular workflow that maps practices onto all stages of research—from discovery and analysis to publication and dissemination. It evokes both technological ingenuity (as one of humanity’s foundational inventions) and hermeneutic process, resonating with the hermeneutic circle’s model of iterative interpretation.

Along with the wheel, the tree metaphor, represented in the FOSTER taxonomy, introduced a hierarchical, systematic framework. The tree provides order and classification, while also carrying deep historical symbolism. As Di Donato reminded us, trees have long served as political emblems of liberty and revolution, from Boston’s Liberty Tree in the American Revolution to Norbert Pressac’s patriotic oak in the French Revolution. (Mancuso and Di Stefano 2018) further underscores the radical significance of living trees as symbols of liberty in contrast to dead nature as signs of despotism.

2.4 The Graph

The **graph** metaphor marks a further step toward systemic complexity. As employed in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), the graph embodies a decentralized topology of vertices

and edges. It reflects the architecture of the internet and highlights three of UNESCO's stated objectives: the universal accessibility of knowledge, the enhancement of collaboration and exchange, and the inclusion of actors beyond traditional scientific institutions. In this image, Open Science is less a taxonomy or workflow than a dynamic, relational network. The graph serves as a conceptual bridge to Di Donato's culminating proposal: the **forest**.

3. The Forest Metaphor: Proposal and Promise

In her presentation, Francesca Di Donato advanced the metaphor of the **forest** as the most comprehensive image yet for articulating Open Science. The forest integrates the strengths of earlier metaphors: it retains the natural vitality of the mushroom, the revolutionary symbolism of the tree, and the interconnected relationality of the graph. It offers a vision of Open Science as a living, collaborative, and intelligent ecosystem, dynamic in its growth and resilient in its diversity.

Di Donato attributed to the forest a set of qualities that align with the highest aspirations of the Open Science movement:

- **Collaboration:** Echoing Peter Kropotkin's theory of mutual aid, the forest is not a site of isolated competition but of mutual support. Trees exchange nutrients, water, and information through subterranean networks, exemplifying distributed reciprocity (Kropotkin 1902).
- **Inclusivity and Biodiversity:** The forest thrives on diversity. Even "dead trees"—analogous to retired datasets or completed projects—retain ecological function, offering nourishment, structure, and continuity.
- **Collective Intelligence:** Contemporary plant science has shown that plants exhibit forms of distributed intelligence. Di Donato extended this insight, describing the forest as a "swarm of swarms," where the intelligence of the whole far exceeds that of individual parts.
- **Value Reorientation:** Drawing on (Mounier 2022), Di Donato suggested that the forest metaphor shifts evaluative criteria in science. Instead of efficiency or excellence, it foregrounds questions such as: Is it sustainable? Is it inclusive? Is it creative? Is it alive?

The forest metaphor thus serves as both emblem and program. It captures the aspirational qualities of openness while offering a systemic image of interdependence. Yet, as I will argue in the following section, its strength lies not only in its celebratory dimension but also in its capacity to make visible the **asymmetries** and inequities that characterize both forests and contemporary knowledge ecosystems.

4. Critical Re-Reading: The Inherent Asymmetries of the Forest

While the forest metaphor captures the collaborative and life-sustaining qualities of Open Science, it risks becoming a romanticized emblem if detached from the realities of both natural and scientific ecosystems. A factual forest is not purely harmonious; it is a site of structural asymmetry, selective advantage, and exclusion. To be pragmatically useful, the metaphor must encompass these dynamics, rather than obscure them. As **Cristina Marras's** work on pragmatic modelling and constitutive

metaphors suggests, images achieve their epistemic force precisely when they expose tensions and guide critical orientation, not when they idealize.

4.1 Structural Asymmetries in Forests and Science

The asymmetries of natural forests provide illuminating parallels for Open Science:

- **Unequal Resource Distribution:** Tall canopy trees monopolize sunlight, limiting growth for understory plants. Similarly, well-funded institutions and Anglophone research networks capture the majority of visibility, funding, and recognition in global knowledge production.
- **Absence of Equal Opportunity:** The survival of a seed depends heavily on the accident of where it falls. Fertile ground yields growth, while otherwise viable seeds perish in shade. Academia reflects a similar contingency, where positional advantages, such as geography, institutional affiliation, and linguistic privilege, shape success more than intrinsic merit.
- **Exclusion and Competition:** Some species practice allelopathy, releasing chemicals to suppress competitors. This parallels the gatekeeping practices of journals, competitive funding regimes, and institutional rivalries that stifle collaboration.
- **Efficiency Without Fairness:** Forests are resilient and efficient, but their efficiency emerges through cycles of dominance, decay, and regrowth, producing winners and losers. Likewise, the scientific system efficiently generates vast amounts of data, but often at the cost of fairness, inclusivity, and sustainability.

4.2 Mapping the Gaps in Open Science

The application of this critical lens reveals a persistent imbalance within the Open Science movement: access asymmetries have been more effectively addressed than evaluative asymmetries. Open-access initiatives have lowered barriers to reading, yet asymmetries in recognition, reward, and linguistic equity remain entrenched. Metrics, infrastructures, and incentive systems continue to privilege dominant actors, leaving systemic inequalities largely intact.

This analysis was shaped through a collaborative group exercise during the workshop with Lottie Provost and Pamela Barletta, where we collectively examined asymmetries and gaps and formulated recommendations. The main value of the forest metaphor, therefore, is not in supporting an idealized openness but in making these tensions visible. By acknowledging the darker dimensions of the forest, the metaphor becomes a diagnostic tool, one that confronts the disjunction between principles and practices in contemporary science.

5. Toward a Constitutive Image: Enriching the Metaphor

For a metaphor to serve as more than illustration, it must move beyond descriptive resonance to become **constitutive**—a framework that structures orientation, shapes collective imagination, and guides practice. In this sense, the forest metaphor is most effective when it acknowledges complexity and asymmetry rather than presenting a simplified, idealized vision. Following **Cristina Marras's** account of pragmatic modelling, metaphors act as “operators” that frame, organize, and make visible the dynamics of a system.

During the Rome workshop, participants engaged in group annotation of Di Donato's forest image, collectively enriching the metaphor by adding layers of nuance. Several key additions emerged from these discussions:

- **Protective Frame:** A boundary around the forest symbolizing the ethical principles, shared values, and commitments, such as multilingualism and pluralism, that sustain and defend the Open Science ecosystem.
- **Facilitators in the Sky:** Birds, bees, and wind were imagined as forces of pollination and cross-pollination, representing the circulation of ideas across communities. In some contributions, artificial intelligence was visualized as an airplane, an artificial but integrated presence capable of connecting otherwise fragmented domains.
- **Cracks and Divides:** A canyon cutting across the ground was added to symbolize digital divides, systemic inequalities, and fragmented infrastructures that prevent the root network from achieving true universality.

My colleague Ramazan Turgut invoked the poet Nâzım Hikmet, suggesting that if individual trees are researchers or institutions, then the **invisible labor** of care, maintenance, and community-building is the glue binding them into a forest. Marras reframed this as unseen photosynthesis: the silent but essential labor that transforms light into energy, sustaining the whole system.

During the discussion, Di Donato expressed a preference for maintaining a simple, easily grasped image. I respectfully disagreed, arguing that metaphors achieve their constitutive power not solely through simplicity, but through a layered complexity. A metaphor must be available at multiple levels of engagement:

- a simple outline for recognition and advocacy,
- a moderately detailed sketch for teaching and orientation, and
- a fully articulated rendering for diagnostic and critical purposes.

As with the **Mona Lisa**, whose apparent simplicity conceals layers of detail and meaning, the forest metaphor benefits from being enriched with visible asymmetries and tensions. Such detail is not a distraction but a necessary feature that enables the metaphor to function both descriptively and prescriptively.

A constitutive metaphor must remain **open**, resisting closure and allowing for diverse interpretations while preserving conceptual coherence. Within this orientation, the forest can function simultaneously as a **mirror** (reflecting the current state of knowledge systems) and as a **maze** (disclosing their complexities, barriers, and inequities). This duality sustains a dynamic interplay between recognition and exploration.

By introducing variability and negotiability, the enriched forest metaphor becomes a **practical tool**: an inclusive framework that supports advocacy, diagnosis, and critique. In this role, it aligns with the spirit of Open Science itself—plural, dynamic, and resistant to reduction.

6. Conclusion: Hope, Pessimism, and the Future

The central argument of this reflection is that the forest metaphor can serve as a profound image for Open Science, but only if it fully embraces its complex, un-romanticized nature. A forest is both cooperative and competitive, both nourishing and exclusionary. Similarly, Open Science must be understood as a system marked by collaboration and aspiration on the one hand, and asymmetry and inequity on the other. Its metaphors must not obscure these contradictions but render them visible.

The workshop at CNR crystallized this duality for me. On the one hand, I encountered a group of scholars whose passion, dedication, and intellectual generosity were deeply inspiring. Their commitment to foundational domains, such as philosophy, linguistics, and epistemology, exemplifies a form of scholarship that is essential yet often undervalued in a global system driven by market logics. Even in brief exchanges over the “fast coffees” that punctuated our day, I witnessed the vitality of a community working collaboratively to rethink the future of science.

On the other hand, I was reminded of the systemic injustices that structure the global knowledge economy. Vast sums are devoted to militarization while scholars committed to open, plural, and inclusive science struggle to secure minimal funding. Reward structures often prioritize metrics over meaning, prestige over pluralism. The hope generated by committed individuals thus coexists with a sober pessimism about entrenched inequities.

I remain grateful to Francesca Di Donato for sharing her work with openness and courage, to Cristina Marras for her intellectual leadership and generosity, and to colleagues including Ramazan Turgut, Lottie Provost, and Pamela Barletta for their insights and collaboration. I eagerly anticipate the publication of Di Donato’s book and the wider conversations it will spark.

Ultimately, the task is not to resolve the tension between hope and pessimism but to inhabit it productively. As scholars, we must hold both: the inspiration of the forest as an emblem of inclusivity and collaboration, and the recognition of its asymmetries as a diagnostic of inequity. Only in this dual perspective can Open Science avoid becoming a romantic ideal and instead realize its transformative potential.

Let us hope that this vision for an open science—or in Persian *دانش باز*—will continue to grow, nourished by plurality, vigilance, and care.

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